

7.1 Country Brief: A social psychological perspective on trends of extremism in Poland

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About the Project

D.Rad is a comparative study of radicalisation and polarisation in Europe and beyond. It aims to identify the actors, networks, and broader social contexts driving radicalisation, particularly among young people in urban and peri-urban areas. D.Rad conceptualises this through the I-GAP spectrum (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarisation) to move towards measurable evaluations of de-radicalisation programmes. We intend to identify the building blocks of radicalisation, including a sense of being victimised, being thwarted or lacking agency in established legal and political structures and coming under the influence of “us vs them” identity formulations.

D.Rad benefits from an exceptional breadth of backgrounds. The project spans national contexts, including the UK, France, Italy, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Finland, Slovenia, Bosnia, Serbia, Kosovo, Israel, Turkey, Georgia, Austria, and several minority nationalisms. It bridges academic disciplines ranging from political science and cultural studies to social psychology and artificial intelligence. Dissemination methods include D.Rad labs, D.Rad hubs, policy papers, academic workshops, visual outputs and digital galleries. As such, D.Rad establishes a rigorous foundation to test practical interventions geared to prevention, inclusion and de-radicalisation.

With the possibility of capturing the trajectories of seventeen nations and several minority nations, the project will provide a unique evidence base for the comparative analysis of law and policy as nation-states adapt to new security challenges. Mapping these varieties and their link to national contexts is crucial in uncovering strengths and weaknesses in existing interventions. Furthermore, D.Rad accounts for the problem that radicalisation processes often occur in circumstances that escape the control and scrutiny of traditional national justice frameworks. The participation of AI professionals in modelling, analysing and devising solutions to online radicalisation is central to the project’s aims.

Executive Summary

This country brief summarises the survey findings for Poland. It then embeds the survey findings within a national and cultural context for each country. The aim of these summaries is to situate the findings within their respective sociopolitical and sociocultural contexts. The literature review and rationale for the proposed model, analysis of the full dataset, and discussion can be found in the full 7.1 report, which also contains the country briefs.

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1. Results

Poland had 30.75% of participants reporting not knowing their political attitudes. This variable was subsequently excluded from the model, keeping all participants and resulting in a final sample of $n = 322$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
24.49 (6.72)	151	46.89	171	53.10	0	0.00

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Christian	244	75.78
Agnostic/Atheist	69	21.43
Other	4	1.24
Buddhist	3	0.93
Jewish	1	0.31
Muslim	1	0.31
Bahá'í	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	60	18.63
No	241	74.84
Don't know	21	6.52

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Gender	24	40.00
Sexuality	21	35.00
Religion	12	20.00
Colour or race	7	11.67
Other	6	10.00

Nationality	4	6.67
Age	4	6.67
Language	2	3.33
Disability	2	3.33
Ethnic group	1	1.67

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	114	35.40	128	39.75	80	24.84
Sport or recreational organization	103	31.99	82	25.47	137	42.55
Art, music or educational organization	94	29.19	84	26.09	144	44.72
Labour union	83	25.78	81	25.16	158	49.07
Political party	32	9.94	100	31.06	190	59.01
Environmental organization	67	20.81	80	24.84	175	54.35
Professional association	67	20.81	77	23.91	178	55.28
Humanitarian or charitable organization	83	25.78	86	26.71	153	47.52
Consumer organization	62	19.25	75	23.29	185	57.45
Self-help group or mutual help group	79	24.53	75	23.29	168	52.17
Women's group	72	22.36	75	23.29	175	54.35
Other organization	26	8.07	51	15.84	245	76.09

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

	Yes		No		Missing value	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Contacted a politician or government official	75	23.29	217	67.39	30	9.32
Worked in a political party or action group	28	8.70	261	81.06	33	10.25
Worked in another ideological organization	31	9.63	259	80.43	32	9.94
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	56	17.39	236	73.29	30	9.32
Signed a petition	149	46.27	143	44.41	30	9.32
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	95	29.50	196	60.87	31	9.63
Boycotted certain products	95	29.50	180	55.90	47	14.60
Posted or shared anything about politics online	116	36.02	176	54.66	30	9.32

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was associated with perceiving migrants as a larger threat to one's national ingroup and its access to resources, welfare, and power. Additionally, perceiving that one's national ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants was also associated with increased perceived threat from migrants.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was associated with increased support for extremist attitudes. Perceiving one's ingroup as being superior to other social groups (collective narcissism) was also linked with increased support for extremist attitudes. Additionally, perceiving that one's ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants was also associated with increased support for extremist attitudes. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing greater social alienation was associated with higher support for extremism; in contrast, experiencing more social cohesion was a protective factor in that experiencing more social cohesion was linked with decreased support for extremism.

Indirect predictors on extremism

Online group identity had an indirect effect on extremist attitudes via collective narcissism and social alienation. A stronger online group identity predicted increased collective narcissism and increased feelings of being socially alienated. These increases, in turn, predicted stronger support for extremist attitudes. The total indirect effect of online group identity (i.e., the sum of *all* indirect effects through other variables, even if these were not statistically significant on their own) was significant; a stronger online group identity predicted increased support for extremist attitudes via the combination of its relationship to the mediating variables in the model (thought note this total indirect effect is mainly driven by the indirect effects of collective narcissism and social alienation).

Figure 14. Respecified model for Poland

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Feelings of social alienation and endorsing more populist attitudes were both separately associated with more negative attitudes towards Russia. Perceiving that migrants are more of a threat to Poland and its resources was, in contrast, linked with more positive views towards Russia. Regarding attitudes towards Russian migrants, endorsing more populist attitudes was associated with worsened opinions towards Russian migrants in the past twelve months. Perceiving that migrants were a greater threat to Poland was linked to worsened opinions towards Ukrainian migrants in the past twelve months.

2. Situating the findings within the Polish context

This chapter situates the findings of the D.Rad questionnaire in the political context of Poland. While other societal and individual aspects are relevant to explaining extremism and radicalisation on an individual or societal level, as evidenced in the literature, the political context is one of the most important macro factors.

The D.Rad survey was conducted in Poland while the country was governed by a right-wing coalition led by Prime Minister Mateusz Morawiecki from the conservative *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość* party. Besides *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość*, which held 237 seats (43.6%), other parliamentary parties were the liberal *Koalicja Obywatelska* (27.4% - 133 seats), the left-wing *Lewica* (12.6% - 47 seats), the agrarian *Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe* (8.6% - 31 seats), the far-right *Konfederacja Wolność i Niepodległość* (6.8% - 11 seats) and *Mniejszość Niemiecka* – a German minority party (0.2% - 1 seat). The last parliamentary elections in Poland took place on October 15, 2023, ending the rule of *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość*.

Typically, in Poland, urban areas are left-wing oriented compared to peri-urban areas. The larger the urban centre, the more support there is for *Koalicja Obywatelska*. *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość* won the 2018 parliamentary elections in the peri-urban with a result of 56.2%, and the *Koalicja Obywatelska* received 16.7% of the votes. Also, in small towns (up to 50,000 inhabitants), *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość* won with the support of 41.7%, while 28.2% voted for *Koalicja Obywatelska*. In the largest cities (over 500,000 inhabitants), 41.1% voted for *Koalicja Obywatelska* and for *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość* – 26.9%. Naturally, *Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe* found the most voters in rural areas; the least support came from urban voters. *Konfederacja* achieved equal results in urban and peri-urban areas.

In terms of the voting patterns in Poland, what is particularly relevant is, although unofficial and oversimplified, the widely recognised and examined distinction between Poland "A" and Poland "B". The region west of the Vistula River, known as Poland "A", has been acknowledged as more developed economically than Poland "B", the part of Poland east of the river. Since the 1990s, Poland "A" tended to support secular and liberal political parties, while voters from Poland "B" (excluding Warsaw) parties represented Christian and conservative political agendas.

The survey indicated that increased perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat predicted worsened opinions towards Ukrainian migrants in the past year. In contrast, increased

populism predicted worsened opinions towards Russian migrants in the past year. This is consistent with current trends in Poland, particularly within right-wing circles. Polish right-wing populism builds on anti-immigrant sentiment. This was particularly evident during the migration wave and EU 'crisis', which invoked Eurosceptic and anti-German views in Poland (Stojarová, 2018). However, this sentiment does not apply equally to all migrants. As a result of the violation of Ukraine's territorial integrity, the position of political parties (both the ruling centre-right and the mainstream opposition parties) regarding the assessment of the political situation was relatively uniform. It included a call for multidimensional aid for Ukraine, condemnation of the aggression, and sanctions against Russia (Sokół, 2022). The contacts between representatives of Polish political parties and political circles in Ukraine intensified - *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość* politicians were active, especially during Euromaidan, and other political elites (especially *Platforma Obywatelska* and *Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe*) were in favour of supporting Ukraine's pro-European aspirations (Mrozek, 2015). The mainstream political circles in Poland had a very clear assessment that the victims of Russian aggression need comprehensive assistance (humanitarian, financial, and military).

In this context, it is also noteworthy to point out Russian propaganda activities in Poland aiming to discredit refugees from Ukraine to create conflicts between Poles and Ukrainian migrants, presenting the latter as a threat to Polish society. As the Government Plenipotentiary for the Security of the Information Space of the Republic of Poland points out (2023), the Kremlin seeks to create an impression that there is widespread opposition in Europe to supporting Ukraine's defence efforts, inspires groups pretending to be a pacifist in various places, as well as spreads disinformation:

The Russians constantly monitor the Polish-language information environment. They are able to dynamically manage the context and give actual events their interpretations to discredit Ukraine or Ukrainians in the eyes of Poles. (...) The Legionella infection in Rzeszów was used by Russian propaganda to attack the perception of Ukraine and the USA by the Poles. The Russians promoted the lie that the bacterium was brought by refugees from Ukraine and that it was the product of experiments in American laboratories.

Relevant is also the finding that increased perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat predicted improved attitudes towards Russia. It is worth pointing out that the more populist and socially alienated the D.Rad-survey respondents were, the worse was their perception towards Russia (e.g., "We should break all cooperation with Russian academics, artists, and athletes."). Most political parties in Poland supported sanctions against the aggressor and aid for Ukraine and its citizens, which was manifested in the documents submitted by the parliamentary majority since the beginning of 2022. Nevertheless, this was not the case with some political circles, such as *Konfederacja*, that lacked broad public support and the ability to influence Polish foreign policy. Despite internal differences, some MPs critiqued the political mainstream's policy towards Ukraine and Ukrainian citizens in Poland, and one member of this party even initiated a 'stop Ukrainization' campaign.

Significant in the context are the findings of the D.Rad survey that showed that age was negatively correlated with extremism, such that older participants had lower support for

extremist attitudes. These findings are consistent with what is known about Polish parties associated with extreme political opinions, as the age cohort most supportive of *Konfederacja* is mainly young men. Moreover, the survey showed that men reported more support for extremist attitudes than women did. This finding is also consistent with the factual situation as Poles arrested for extremism, similar to other parts of the world, also tend to be younger and male (Agency of Interior Security, 2023), with perpetrators representing both right-wing and left-wing political extremism.

Wiech (2023), explaining the popularity of *Konfederacja* among young Polish men, pointed out that this group has been virtually unnoticed by all major political forces in recent years. The Programme 500 Plus, which gained votes for *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość*, among other groups, is not appealing to young men who either do not have children yet or believe these kinds of social programs are unfair towards them. The popularity of *Konfederacja* is also the result of the anti-campaign by *Prawo i Sprawiedliwość* and *Koalicja Obywatelska*, who limited their campaign to threatening scenarios of what will happen if the opponent stays in power or gains it. Wiech further clarifies that *Konfederacja* managed to understand the needs of young men who enter the labour market and run a campaign of promises accordingly. These promises are largely unrealistic ('low and simple taxes', 'voluntary social insurance', rejection of the EU's climate policy') and do not seem concerned about financing, the long-term effects, or even legal mechanisms for their implementation. At the same time, they can reach frustrated young males skillfully through social media, TikTok or organising pub meetings with party leaders.

The results of the D.Rad survey that increased perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat predicted improved attitudes towards Russia could be interpreted in the context of Kremlin propaganda and lack of empathy coupled with displaying anxiety over scarce economic resources. What is more, the participants who belonged to discriminated groups reported more improved opinions towards Ukrainian migrants in the last 12 months than participants who did not belong to discriminated groups did, whose opinions remained primarily unchanged. While society has been divided over the issues of migration and relation towards the EU, the issue of Ukrainian migrants seems less polarising. There is no doubt that Polish-Ukrainian relations in previous years were present both in official party programs and in the statements of party leaders with the same postulates (Sokol, 2022).

The interpretation of the D.Rad survey was conducted here in the context of the political situation, which helped to evaluate the most important macro factors. However, it is also worth pointing out that other relevant factors are likely to have an impact. Moreover, the political climate, consisting of the views of individual political parties on many issues, is not constant but transforms depending on the changing international situation and the internal situation in other countries, e.g., Ukraine.

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